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A Meta-Analysis On Audio-Visuals In Educational Enhancement And Teaching In Secondary Schools

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ABSTRACT

The integration of audio-visuals in secondary school education has been a topic of increasing interest and debate. This meta-analysis synthesizes findings from a range of studies to explore the effects of audio-visual aids on educational enhancement and teaching effectiveness in secondary schools. This analysis focuses on the effectiveness of the use of audio-visuals aids in secondary schools highlighting their benefits as well as challenges. In this review, 110 articles and publications were selected from different databases such as Web of Science, PubMed, and Google Scholar using keywords like "audio-visual," "teaching," "educational enhancement," and "secondary schools." Out of the 110 assessed articles and publications, about 33 were selected based on the keywords chosen by the author. The findings contribute to our understanding of how audio-visual tools can be optimally utilized to support pedagogical practices and improve educational outcomes in secondary education settings. The author makes recommendations on how secondary schools can harness the benefits for audio-visuals aids to maximize its impacts in the learning process of secondary school students.

Keywords: Audio-visual, educational enhancement, teaching aids, secondary school

INTRODUCTION

Times have changed when students are viewed as those whose main role is just to receive information from the teachers whom they perceive to be masters of knowledge and wisdom. The world is now a global village with Information Communication Technology (ICT) which now gives the student an opportunity to make more and personal research on what has been taught in class to further buttress the points made by their teacher. The age of digitalization has brought a stimulating factor to the development of Audio-Visual technology (Clark and Mayer, 2016). The materials such as: computers, power point, video set, television, radio used by teachers to teach in the primary and secondary school levels of our education system, are important issues that needs to be taken seriously to have a successful transfer of knowledge from the students to the teachers (Mayer, 2009). Audio-Visual technology has been used for decades but in limited ways whereby short educational films are played on video players and TV.

In our world today, we have the computer being used to play educational films and homework given in school are also being done increasingly on Pcs. Some research carried out by various researchers show that the young people nowadays spend more than 4-5 hours a day in front of media such as television, computer, video, and video games (Woodard and Gridina, 2000; Hohlfeld, et al., 2010). The status of Audio-Visual aids has risen from mere saying to more professional enterprise. Therefore, the approaches of teaching and learning adopted during the time of our forefathers are no longer what we have now.

The integration of audio-visual aids in education has been a transformative approach, revolutionizing traditional teaching methods and enhancing the learning experience for students. Audio-visual tools, including videos, interactive software, and digital presentations, provide dynamic and engaging ways to

present information, catering to diverse learning styles (Mayer, 2009). In secondary schools, where students are at a critical stage of cognitive and social development, the use of these tools can significantly enhance understanding and retention of complex concepts (Kaur, 2015). The use of teaching aids is important to both the music teacher and the music students. Learning experiences and activities must be understandable in the personal life of the learner as well as arranged in a way that the learners have some degree of confidence and success in their work.

This article is motivated by the failure of how many schools are hesitant to recognize the benefits that technology offers to children who are in contact with them every day. This has so greatly affected pupil's interest or stimulation in learning thereby negatively affecting teaching and learning in Nigeria secondary schools. Teaching and learning in this millennium have gone beyond presenting learning materials to the students in such a way that they are viewed as passive learners who cannot contribute meaningfully during the teaching-learning process. It has gone beyond teaching without instructional aid to assist the learners to retain the information being conveyed (Kaur, 2015).

Most schools are yet to enjoy using Audio-Visuals to its full potentials probably due to insufficient fund to provide the resources, inadequacy and incompetency in its usage. Inadequate use of Audio-visual resources deters effective teaching and learning at Secondary level, which consequently lowers academic performance of the pupils and their zeal to higher education. If nothing is done to create awareness on the need to use audio-visual resource in teaching and learning at Secondary school, the nation's labour force will be affected in the long run and the entire nation will suffer poor socio-political and economic development. It is against this background that this study aims at investigating Audio-Visual resources in classrooms as an enhancement tool for effective teaching and learning in Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt. Sadly, some educators in Nigeria lack these skills because they are not informed about the changes as regards to the teaching and learning. The realization that the use of words alone, cannot and will not be enough for pupils by an experienced teacher, helps the pupils get vivid learning experience provided by the teacher.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

The effectiveness of audio-visual aids in education is grounded in several theoretical frameworks. One such theory is Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory, which posits that individuals learn more effectively from words and pictures than from words alone (Mayer, 2009). This theory is supported by the cognitive load theory, which suggests that learning is optimized when information is presented in a way that reduces cognitive overload (Sweller, 1988). By combining visual and auditory elements, audio-visual aids can distribute cognitive processing across multiple channels, thereby enhancing comprehension and retention.

The Psychology of using Audio-Visual aids

It is generally believed that the best learning takes place when the greatest number of senses are stimulated. Psychologist have long recognized the importance of concrete illustration in teaching. The introduction of a device is an incentive used to help in stimulating the pupil and developing understanding through experiencing. Modern media are among the tools the modern teachers utilize in promoting growth and development of pupils. These devices, visual or audio-visual materials, are valuable in the learning-teaching process because they stimulate interest and make possible the enrichment of the pupil's experience. The learning process becomes more meaningful when there's constant improvement on the methods and devices used by good teachers.

The use of various instructions devices or audio-visual materials should be provided to develop understanding. A good number of educators admit that some people are able to comprehend abstractly, while others are more dependent upon concrete materials as aid to thought that is to say, the lower the mentality, the greater the dependence upon visual imagery as a medium of thought (Hattie, 2009). These educational aids can be divided into three forms which are; 'printed', 'visual', and 'audio-visual'. Printed

aids are obviously the most widely used aids in education. This is possibly the most popular teaching aid because of its easy accessibility. Printed aids such as, colouring books, textbooks, magazines etc. are cheap aids that can easily be produced and used by the majority (Hattie, 2009). The second form comprises of pictures (graphs, conceptual maps), overhead projectors, boards, data shows and projectors. Diascopes and slides, charts, pictures and illustrated books (Hattie, 2009). The third form comprises video cassettes, motion pictures, cameras, television, computers and computer software, audio-visual aids which apply to the internet. Through these aids, the events and things in the real world are carried to the class in the most realistic way (Hattie, 2009).

Mkpa (2014) sees Audio-Visual aids as resource materials used in facilitating learning by saving instructor's time and effort, capturing learner's interest. Promoting effective retention of subject matter learned, keeping students busy and active and stimulating imagination. Ofoefuna (2017) stated that Audio-Visual aid is a device or instrument which is carefully and deliberately employed by the teacher in the teaching and learning process to convey meaning and facilitate effective teaching and proper understanding.

Audio-visual resources are non-print instructional materials that command the attention of dual sense organs to promote effectiveness in teaching and learning process. They are the product of advanced technology, some of which usually require special equipment to operate, (Aina, and Adekanye, 2013). Audio-visual resources include television, computer and films and the like. These resources are capable to ensure effective teaching which improves skill acquisition and retention among learners especially at the prime level. The use of audio-visual resources in teaching and learning will move teaching method from rote method (teacher center method) to a more innovative and enriched method known as "child center method" Child center method of teaching is a method used in conquering the limitations characterizing the traditional method of teaching. Child center method makes a child an active participant in a classroom setting as it encourages pleasurable learning through the use of audio-visual resources and other instructional devices.

However, despite the roles of audio-visual resources in teaching and learning, Adakole, Eiriemiokhale, and Nnaji (2016) reported that the resources are always provided at a very low level in most schools in the country, which eventually affect the standard of teaching and learning. Due to the poor state of audio-visual resources in the study area, teaching in most of the primary schools is still based on teacher-centered method a method that pays less attention to pupils' individual needs and makes them passive learners.

According to Gibson (1997) such teaching method is abstractive in nature. He further added that, an abstract nature of teaching does not relate the learner to the real world; it neither helps them to think about realistic situation nor encouraged them to generate and pose their own solution. For this reason, most pupils become unmotivated and unconnected thereby developing negative attitude towards learning which consequently affects their academic performance.

It is generally admitted by educators that some people are able to comprehend abstractly, while others are dependent on solid materials as aids to thought. It has also been generally recognized that the more brilliant an individual is, the greater his power for abstract thinking, the lower the mentality, the greater the dependence on visual imagery as a medium of thought. Since most people are visual learners, it's important to go beyond spoken words when educating students. Modern trends have changed the view of educational world that demands each educator to be creative in explaining the materials used in the classroom (Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010).

Allen and Bacon (2004) state that Audio-Visual materials provide a wide range of various musical and dramatic experiences which carry the stimulus mode of sound and picture to the student for promoting better planning and scheduling, giving the teacher more time for supervision, guidance, co-ordination and correction of student's work. Omuku (2017) asserted that music literacy should be taught without any challenges. In his research, he also cited Jerome Brunet (cited in Omuku 2017) who describes discovery methods as a progressive method of teaching whereby children learn freely and discover methods that

will help them remember knowledge and concepts discovered on their own. Years back, the most approaches like the lecture method of teaching used by teachers, only focused on teacher-centered learning which resulted in producing passive students in learning. Every child has the skill to be creative. In order to enhance this skill, the child's senses should be trained first (Gonen, 1998).

Onyejemezie (2014) reveals that audio-visual aids do not achieve any of the attributed values on their own; their usefulness and impact depend on what the teacher makes out of them. Having the knowledge and manipulative skills of using these materials are absolutely necessary. Audio-visuals complement the teachers' use of selected teaching methods by clarifying and simplifying the communication, arousing interest and attention leading to motivation, concrete understanding and enforcement of communicated information (Naidu, 2018). Audio-visuals allows students to learn at their own rate and encourage integrated individual and group learning. They also bring before the learners what otherwise could have looked imaginary, challenging the sense of creativity and making teaching-learning situation more pleasurable, meaningful and effective.

The study research carried out by Idris (2015) on the use of Audio-Visual materials in teaching and learning of classification of living things among senior secondary students raised the need to address those factors affecting Audio-Visual aids used in teaching and learning of science in order to integrate its use in the teaching and learning in schools.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Literature Search Strategy: A comprehensive literature search was conducted using databases such as Web of Science, PubMed, and Google Scholar. Keywords included "audio-visual," "teaching," "educational enhancement," and "secondary schools." Studies were selected based on relevance, recency, and methodological rigor.

Data Extraction: The author selected 110 publications on the use of audio-visuals in educational enhancement and teaching. Out of the 110 publications, 33 publications were deemed fit for this analysis. Data was extracted focusing on audio-visuals, educational enhancement secondary schools.

Meta-Analysis Techniques: Excel tool was employed for data extraction and analysis. The data structure was based on the keywords for each assessed article and the empirical results are displayed below.

EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

Numerous studies have demonstrated the positive impact of audio-visual aids on educational outcomes in secondary schools. For instance, a study by Kaur (2015) found that the use of video clips in teaching science significantly improved students' understanding and retention of complex concepts compared to traditional lecture methods. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Hattie (2009) revealed that the use of multimedia presentations in classrooms had a substantial effect on student achievement, particularly in subjects requiring visualization, such as mathematics and physics.

In a more specific example, a study conducted by Zhang et al. (2006) examined the use of interactive multimedia in a high school biology class. The results indicated that students who were taught using interactive multimedia scored significantly higher on tests of conceptual understanding than those who were taught using traditional methods. This finding suggests that the interactive nature of audio-visual aids can facilitate deeper engagement with the material, leading to better learning outcomes.

Furthermore, audio-visual aids have been shown to support diverse learning styles, making education more inclusive. Gardner's Multiple Intelligences Theory (Gardner, 1983) highlights that students possess different kinds of intelligences and learn best through different modalities. Audio-visual tools can cater to visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners, thereby enhancing overall classroom inclusivity and effectiveness.

Challenges and Limitations

Despite the documented benefits, the implementation of audio-visual aids in secondary education is not without challenges. One significant barrier is the lack of access to adequate resources and infrastructure. In many schools, particularly those in underfunded areas, the availability of modern audio-visual equipment and reliable internet access is limited. This disparity can create a digital divide, where students in resource-rich environments gain more benefits from audio-visual aids than those in resource-poor settings (Hohlfeld et al., 2010).

Another challenge is the potential for over-reliance on audio-visual aids, which can lead to passive learning. When used excessively or inappropriately, these tools can detract from critical thinking and problem-solving skills, as students may become accustomed to receiving information passively rather than actively engaging with the content (Salomon, 1984). It is essential for educators to balance the use of audio-visual aids with interactive and participatory teaching methods.

Additionally, the effectiveness of audio-visual aids depends on the quality of the content and the pedagogical skills of the teacher. Poorly designed multimedia resources or ineffective integration into the curriculum can diminish the potential benefits of these tools (Clark & Mayer, 2016). Teachers need adequate training and professional development to effectively incorporate audio-visual aids into their teaching strategies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To maximize the benefits of audio-visual aids in secondary education, several best practices and recommendations can be followed. Firstly, it is crucial to ensure that audio-visual tools are used to complement, rather than replace, traditional teaching methods. A blended approach that integrates multimedia resources with interactive discussions and hands-on activities can provide a well-rounded learning experience.

Educators should also prioritize the quality and relevance of audio-visual content. Selecting high-quality, curriculum-aligned resources that are pedagogically sound can enhance the learning experience. Collaborating with educational technologists and content developers can help teachers curate and create effective multimedia materials.

Professional development and training for teachers are essential for the successful integration of audio-visual aids. Workshops and training sessions on the use of educational technology can equip teachers with the necessary skills and confidence to utilize these tools effectively (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010). Moreover, creating a supportive community of practice where teachers can share experiences and strategies can foster continuous improvement and innovation in the use of audio-visual aids.

Furthermore, addressing the digital divide is critical to ensuring equitable access to audio-visual resources. Policymakers and educational administrators should invest in infrastructure and resources to provide all schools with the necessary tools and connectivity. Public-private partnerships and grants can also play a role in bridging the gap and ensuring that all students have access to the benefits of audio-visual education.

CONCLUSION

The use of audio-visual aids in secondary education offers significant potential for enhancing teaching and learning. Empirical evidence supports the effectiveness of these tools in improving student understanding, engagement, and achievement. However, challenges such as resource disparities, potential over-reliance, and the need for teacher training must be addressed to fully realize the benefits. By adopting best practices and ensuring equitable access, educators can harness the power of audio-visual aids to create a more dynamic, inclusive, and effective learning environment. Future research should continue to explore innovative ways to integrate audio-visual tools in education, focusing on long-term outcomes and the development of critical 21st-century skills.

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